

Autoignition flames transfer matrix modeling

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Abstract

Modern gas turbines need to fulfill increasingly stringent pollutants emission targets. Ansaldo Energia GT26 and GT36 respond to this by means of the lean-premixed combustion technology and a sequential combustion system. In particular, the second combustion chamber relies on the autoignition principle for flame stabilization. To guarantee high efficiency and, at the same time, ensure operational flexibility it is necessary to study the thermoacoustics of these flames. In this paper, we make use of the linearized Rankine-Hugoniot conditions, a commonly used theoretical approach for propagation flames, to predict an autoignition flame transfer matrix. In particular, we derive the linearized Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions taking into account the presence of a moving discontinuity and upstream entropy inhomogeneities. The obtained analytical expression is compared with large eddy simulations with good agreement. Physical differences with propagation flames are pointed out.

Keywords: autoignition flames, flame transfer matrix

1. Introduction

Modern gas turbines have to fulfill stringent emission limits, guarantee high efficiencies and operate at variable load conditions with various fuels. Ansaldo Energia GT26 and GT36 address these challenging requirements by means of the sequential combustion architecture guaranteeing unmatched operational flexibility [1]. In this framework, the flame stabilization and thermoacoustics of the reheat combustor require an in-depth understanding of the combustion and fluid dynamics physics. In this paper, we focus on the reheat combustor thermoacoustic modeling extending the classic flame transfer matrix model to autoignition stabilized flames, showing how these differ from propagation stabilized flames and which effects become dominant and cannot be neglected [2].

The use of flame transfer matrices (FTM) to provide a compact, black-box description of the flame response to acoustic fluctuations is widely spread. It lumps the complex flame characterization in a set of transfer functions relating up- and downstream acoustic quantities. These functions provide a broadband quantitative description of the system and are easily utilized in network models [3] to predict the overall system behavior. The first derivation of the jumping conditions across a flame front dates from 1953, when Chu [4] analytically derived them from the more general Rankine-Hugoniot (RH) conditions. Different simplifications and versions of these relations, taking into account other parameters not originally modeled, followed from there on, see for example [5]. Different procedures have been proposed to experimentally determine flame transfer matrices, see, e.g., [6]. The experimentally retrieved FTM can be then compared to theoretical models [6], integrated in acoustic network models and used to assess the closed loop system stability [3]. On the numerical side, different works document the possibility of extracting the flame transfer matrix from CFD simulations. Polifke *et al.* [7] describe a numerical methodology based on the inversion of the Wiener-Hopf equation that will become a consolidated tool and that has been lately successfully applied to reheat combustors [2, 8].

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Figure 1: Backward-facing step used for LES simulations, figure adapted from Bothien *et al.* [2].

The interest for autoignition flames has been growing in the last decade. Different works have investigated the thermoacoustic properties of these flames, tackling the flame sensitivity to pressure fluctuations [2, 8, 9], the competition between autoignition and propagation [10], the flame transfer function characterization in the linear and nonlinear regime [2, 8, 9].

In contrast to propagation stabilized flames, only very few works [9] exist investigating analytical modelling approaches for autoignition flames. In this paper, an analytical description for the FTM of autoignition flames is derived and successfully validated with CFD results.

2. The numerical simulations

The numerical simulations results we will use in Section 4 have been obtained and already presented by Bothien *et al.* [2]. In this section, we briefly describe the geometry, the numerical set up, the chemistry model and the system identification methodology.

2.1. Geometry, numerical setup and combustion model

The backward-facing step (BFS) of Fig. 1 is the simplified model of a reheat combustor. Perfectly premixed air and methane are injected through the inlet of the domain, on the bottom surface a no-slip boundary condition assures the presence of a boundary layer, periodic boundary conditions are applied on the two sides and the top plane is a symmetry plane for the flow. The outlet is non-reflecting with respect to acoustic waves. The geometry has been meshed with 2.11 million hexahedral cells and the simulations have been run on the commercial software ANSYS Fluent v17.0. To model the turbulence scales smaller than the mesh the Smagorinsky-Lilly subgrid-scale model with dynamic stress, dynamic energy flux and a Prandtl number of 0.85 have been used. The combustion model relies on tabulated chemistry and a progress variable and is particularly suited to study autoignition flames dynamics. Three compressible simulations have been run, exciting the outlet pressure, the inlet temperature and the inlet velocity respectively. The excitation is provided in form of a low-pass filtered discrete random binary signal (DRBS), which allows a frequency broadband excitation of the flame.

2.2. System identification methodology

The system identification methodology is well explained and successfully tested in a number of works [7, 8] and can be summarized as follows:

1. Velocity, pressure and temperature signals are extracted at a number of different axial location as time-dependent section-averaged quantities. Each signal is shifted to a reference location applying a characteristic-based filter (CBF). This methodology is able to filter out turbulent noise and retain only the meaningful signal information.

2. The flame is assumed to behave as a linear time invariant system. The inputs to this system are the upstream velocity, pressure and temperature signals, the output is the volume-integrated heat release rate. The finite impulse responses (FIR) of the system are calculated from its inputs and output information using the Wiener-Hopf equation [7, 8]. The FIR transformed in the frequency domain provide the flame transfer functions (FTF) F_u , F_p and F_T , for the velocity, pressure and temperature respectively:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}'}{\dot{Q}} = F_p \frac{p'_1}{p_1} + F_u \frac{u'_1}{u_1} + F_T \frac{T'_1}{T_1} \quad (1)$$

3. To identify the FTM the same system identification procedure is applied, considering in this case as output signals the downstream velocity, pressure and temperature fluctuations. Nine frequency-dependent functions F_{ij} are obtained, relating up- to downstream fluctuations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_2}{\rho_2 c_2} \\ u'_2 \\ \frac{RT'_2}{c_2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} & F_{13} \\ F_{21} & F_{22} & F_{23} \\ F_{31} & F_{32} & F_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

More detailed information on the numerical setup and the system identification can be found in [2].

3. The Rankine-Hugoniot conditions

The Rankine-Hugoniot conditions are one-dimensional integral conditions describing the mass, momentum and energy conservation across a discontinuity; in the present case a flame. The discontinuity can be modeled either as still or as in motion. In reheat flames the flame front position is highly sensible to the modification of the autoignition delay time of the unburnt mixture, which is caused by the applied boundary condition excitations. Modeling this phenomenon is crucial for autoignition flames (see Section 4), differently from propagation flames [3]. We assume therefore the flame to move with an absolute velocity u_{fl} . Following integral equations of conservation relate the up- and downstream quantities:

$$u_{fl} \Delta \rho = \Delta(\rho u) \quad \text{Conservation of mass} \quad (3a)$$

$$u_{fl} \Delta(\rho u) = \Delta(\rho u^2 + p) \quad \text{Conservation of momentum} \quad (3b)$$

$$u_{fl} \Delta \left(\rho \left(c_v T + \frac{1}{2} u^2 \right) \right) = \Delta \left(\rho u \left(c_p T + \frac{1}{2} u^2 \right) \right) - \dot{Q} \quad \text{Conservation of energy} \quad (3c)$$

where we introduced the heat release rate of the flame per unit area \dot{Q} . The symbol Δ denotes the difference between quantities in 2 and in 1, e.g. $\Delta p = p_2 - p_1$. For closure, to the set of eqs. (3), one needs to add a state equation, in this case the ideal gas law:

$$p_i = \rho_i R T_i \quad i=1,2 \quad (4a)$$

The system given by eqs. (3) together with eq. (4)(i=2) is a nonlinear algebraic system of four equations in four unknowns, the downstream quantities u_2, P_2, ρ_2, T_2 .

3.1. Linearization

Acoustic disturbances are small perturbations with respect to the mean value. Since we are interested in those small disturbances, we can linearize eqs. (3). Each physical quantity can be written as a sum of a mean constant value and a small fluctuation, for example:

$$p(x, t) = \bar{p} + p'(x, t) \quad (5)$$

where $(\bar{\cdot})$ denotes the mean quantity and $(\cdot)'$ the fluctuation. For sake of simplicity, we drop the overbar from here on. All quantities not denoted with $(\cdot)'$ are meant to be mean values. From the linearization, we obtain two sets of equations, one for the mean quantities:

$$\rho_2 u_2 = \rho_1 u_1 \quad (6a)$$

$$\rho_2 u_2^2 + p_2 = \rho_1 u_1^2 + p_1 \quad (6b)$$

$$\rho_2 u_2 (c_p T_2 + u_2^2/2) = \rho_1 u_1 (c_p T_1 + u_1^2/2) + \dot{Q} \quad (6c)$$

$$p_2/(\rho_2 T_2) = p_1/(\rho_1 T_1) = R \quad (6d)$$

and one for the fluctuating ones:

$$\Delta(\rho' u - \rho u') = u'_{fl}(\rho_2 - \rho_1) \quad (7a)$$

$$\Delta(p' + \rho u u' + u^2 \rho') = 0 \quad (7b)$$

$$\Delta(\rho u (c_p T' + u u')) = \dot{Q}' + \frac{\dot{Q}}{\rho_1 u_1} [u'_{fl} \rho_1 - (\rho'_1 u_1 + \rho_1 u'_1)] - u'_{fl} \Delta p \quad (7c)$$

$$p'_2/p_2 = \rho'_2/\rho_2 + T'_2/T_2 \quad (7d)$$

In the linearization, we have assumed that the mean flame velocity is zero i.e., $u_{fl} = 0$, since the inlet parameters perturbation exciting the flame has zero mean value.

3.2. Solution for the mean quantities

First, we focus exclusively on the mean quantities problem, given in eqs. (6). These are nonlinear algebraic coupled equations with the unknowns u_2, p_2, ρ_2, T_2 . The flame front movement u_{fl} is not present because of the assumption of zero mean flame velocity. The system can be solved analytically and the solution expanded in the Mach number [4]:

$$\frac{u_2}{u_1} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{T_2}{T_1} = 1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{\dot{Q}}{P_1 u_1} + O(M_1^2) \quad (8a)$$

$$\frac{p_2}{p_1} = 1 - (\gamma - 1) \frac{\dot{Q}}{p_1 u_1} M_1^2 + O(M_1^3) \quad (8b)$$

It is interesting to note that, if we had considered from the beginning a problem without moving discontinuity, these relations would hold for the general $u(x, t), p(x, t), \rho(x, t), T(x, t)$ and not only for their mean values $\bar{u}, \bar{p}, \bar{\rho}, \bar{T}$. In many works, see [3, 7], eqs. (8) are linearized:

$$u'_2 = u'_1 + \left(\frac{T_2}{T_1} - 1 \right) u_1 \left(\frac{\dot{Q}'}{\dot{Q}} - \frac{p'_1}{p_1} \right) \quad (9a)$$

$$p'_2 = p'_1 - \left(\frac{T_2}{T_1} - 1 \right) \rho_1 u_1^2 \left(\frac{\dot{Q}'}{\dot{Q}} + \frac{u'_1}{u_1} \right) \quad (9b)$$

Since in the current framework the flame is changing its axial location due to the ignition delay time dependence on temperature, eqs. (9) are not valid.

3.3. Solution for the fluctuating quantities

Rewriting eqs. (7) using as independent variables the scaled pressure fluctuation $p'/(c\rho)$, the scaled temperature fluctuation RT'/c and the velocity fluctuations u' one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{bmatrix} \gamma M_1 \frac{c_1}{c_2} & \frac{u_1}{u_2} & -\gamma M_1 \frac{c_1}{c_2} \\ \frac{c_1}{c_2} \frac{p_2}{p_1} + \gamma M_1 M_2 & 2M_1 & -\gamma M_1 M_2 \\ 0 & \gamma M_1^2 \frac{u_2}{u_1} & \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma-1} M_1 \frac{c_2}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_2}{\rho_2 c_2} \\ u'_2 \\ \frac{RT'_2}{c_2} \end{bmatrix} = \\ & = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma M_1 & 1 & -\gamma M_1 \\ 1 + \gamma M_1^2 & 2M_1 & -\gamma M_1^2 \\ -\frac{\dot{Q}}{u_1 p_1} \gamma M_1 & \gamma M_1^2 - \frac{\dot{Q}}{p_1 u_1} & \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma-1} M_1 + \frac{\dot{Q}}{u_1 p_1} \gamma M_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\dot{Q}}{u_1 p_1} \end{bmatrix} u_1 \frac{\dot{Q}}{Q} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{u_1}{u_2} - 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 - \frac{p_2}{p_1} + \frac{\dot{Q}}{p_1 u_1} \end{bmatrix} u'_{fl} \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (10) provides the downstream fluctuations as function of the upstream ones. We focus now on the last two summands and try to express \dot{Q}' and u'_{fl} as functions of the upstream quantities $p'_1/(c_1\rho_1)$, RT'_1/c_1 and u'_1 .

3.3.1. Solution for the unsteady heat release

For the unsteady relative heat release fluctuations $\frac{\dot{Q}'}{Q}$ we assume the single FTFs relating the upstream quantities $p'_1/(c_1\rho_1)$, RT'_1/c_1 and u'_1 to it, to be known. Equation (1) hence yields:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}'}{Q} = F_p \frac{p'_1}{p_1} + F_u \frac{u'_1}{u_1} + F_T \frac{T'_1}{T_1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\gamma}{c_1} F_p & \frac{1}{u_1} F_u & \frac{\gamma}{c_1} F_T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

3.3.2. Solution for the moving flame

For modelling the dependence of u'_{fl} on the upstream fluctuations we assume the flame to be a thin discontinuity between the unburnt and the burnt mixture. With this model the heat release rate per unit area will depend on the amount of fuel crossing the flame per unit time, i.e. the relative velocity between the flame and the flow, and on the density of this fuel. This means:

$$\dot{Q} = \rho_1 (u_1 - u_{fl}) H_F \quad (12)$$

where H_F is the constant lower heating value of the considered fuel. If the flame moves downstream, the relative velocity between the mean flow and the flame is reduced and \dot{Q} is smaller. The opposite happens for a flame moving upstream. We linearize eq. (12) around the mean condition (with $u_{fl} = 0$):

$$\frac{\dot{Q}'}{\dot{Q}} = \frac{\rho'_1}{\rho_1} + \frac{u'_1}{u_1} - \frac{u'_{fl}}{u_1} \quad (13)$$

Combining eq. (13) and eq. (11) we can extract the fluctuating flame velocity:

$$u'_{fl} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma M_1 (1 - F_p) & (1 - F_u) & -\gamma M_1 (1 + F_T) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

3.3.3. The small Mach number approximation

Equation (10) can be expanded introducing eq. (11) for the unsteady heat release rate and eq. (14) for the moving flame. For small Mach numbers, a first order approximation of eqs. (8) yield:

$$\frac{u_2}{u_1} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{T_2}{T_1} = \lambda \triangleq 1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma} \frac{\dot{Q}}{p_1 u_1} \quad (15a)$$

$$\frac{p_2}{p_1} = 1 \quad (15b)$$

Figure 2: Flame transfer functions of the simulated autoignition flames, eq. (1). Result reproduced from Bothien *et al.* [2].

Substituting eqs. (15) in eq. (10), inverting the matrix on the left hand side and neglecting all terms of third order or higher in Mach number we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_2}{\rho_2 c_2} \\ u'_2 \\ \frac{RT'_2}{c_2} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{\lambda} + \sqrt{\lambda}\gamma M_1^2(\lambda - 1) & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma M_1(1 - \lambda) & 1 + (\lambda - 1)(1 - \gamma)M_1^2 & 0 \\ (\lambda - 1)(\gamma - 1)\sqrt{\lambda}M_1^2 & \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma}M_1 \frac{1 - \lambda}{\sqrt{\lambda}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} + \dots \\
 \dots + \begin{bmatrix} 2M_1^2\gamma(1 - \lambda)\sqrt{\lambda}F_p & 2\sqrt{\lambda}M_1(1 - \lambda)F_u & 2M_1^2\gamma(1 - \lambda)\sqrt{\lambda}F_T \\ \gamma M_1(\lambda - 1)F_p & (\lambda - 1)F_u + (\gamma + 1)(\lambda - 1)\lambda M_1^2 F_u & \gamma M_1(\lambda - 1)F_T \\ (\gamma - 1)(1 - \lambda)\sqrt{\lambda}M_1^2 F_p & \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma}\sqrt{\lambda}(1 - \lambda)M_1 F_u & (\gamma - 1)(1 - \lambda)\sqrt{\lambda}M_1^2 F_T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p'_1}{\rho_1 c_1} \\ u'_1 \\ \frac{RT'_1}{c_1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)
 \end{aligned}$$

where λ is defined in eq. (15a) and is a constant value. One could argue that we are using a first order approximation for the mean quantities and a second order for the fluctuating ones. We will see that, even if the Mach number is small, the first order approximation is insufficient for the characteristics of reheat flames.

4. Results discussion

In Fig. 2, the FTF F_u , F_p and F_T as defined in eq. (1) and identified in Bothien *et al.* [2] are shown. The F_p and F_T elements present a large gain, as discussed in other works on autoignition flames [2, 8, 9]. The F_u element is instead small, differently from propagation flames.

In Fig. 3, the analytic result given in eq. (16) (orange, dashed line) is compared to the LES results from [2] (blue, solid line). The agreement is excellent for all elements. Significant differences are present only in the phase of the elements (1, 2), (3, 1) and (3, 2). This is due to the fact that the corresponding gains are small and hence the phase estimation is error-prone. All elements with gains larger than 0.5 are well reproduced also in the phase behavior. This confirms the correctness of eq. (16). Additionally:

- Figure 3 verifies the consistency of the system identification methodology applied by means of a completely independent analytical approach.
- Each column of the FTM depends on a single element of the flame transfer function, therefore there are no cross dependencies between FTF elements in the FTM. This is to be expected since a linear framework is considered.

Figure 3: Flame transfer matrix from LES [2] (blue, solid line), analytic formulation of eq. (16) (orange, dashed line) and classical model eq. (9) (yellow, dotted line).

- The first order in the Mach number approximation (yellow, dotted line) from the original work of Chu [4] predicts a zero gain for the element (1, 3). Equation (16) (orange, dashed line) instead correctly reproduce the numerical result (blue, solid line). This shows that, even if the simulated Mach number is small, second order terms in the Mach number must be retained because reheat flames are highly sensible to temperature fluctuations and present large gains F_T in the FTF.
- Beside exhibiting increased gains, reheat flames are characterized by non-negligible oscillations with respect to their mean position even for small inlet parameters perturbations. The flame velocity fluctuation term, u'_{fl} , is capturing this contribution. When dealing with thermoacoustics of propagation flames this term can be neglected without affecting the results significantly [3]. This is not possible for reheat flames, see the yellow dotted curve in the last row of Fig. 3.
- The classic eqs. (9) (yellow dotted curve), successfully used in literature [3], is not able to correctly reproduce the LES results. This is because it is not taking into account the second order terms in the Mach number and the flame velocity term u_{fl} .

5. Conclusions

The theoretical approach provided by the linearized Rankine-Hugoniot conditions has been widely applied to propagation flames [3, 6], both for experimental and numerical studies. In this paper, for the first time, we apply the same method to a numerically computed reheat flame [2] and we predict the FTM starting from the known flame transfer functions. We observe that the linearized Rankine-Hugoniot conditions maintain a good FTM prediction capability provided that: terms of second order in the Mach number are retained and the flame speed fluctuations are properly modeled. These two features are related to the sensibility of reheat flames to temperature fluctuations and hence cannot be neglected in autoignition flames. We also highlight how the classic equations found in literature (eqs. (9)) are not sufficiently accurate.

- [1] D. A. Pennell, M. R. Bothien, A. Ciani, V. Granet, G. Singla, S. Thorpe, A. Wickstroem, K. Oumejjoud, M. Yaquinto, An Introduction to the Ansaldo GT36 Constant Pressure Sequential Combustor, in: ASME Paper No. GT2017-64790, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA, 2017. doi:10.1115/GT2017-64790. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2017-64790>
- [2] M. Bothien, D. Lauper, Y. Yang, A. Scarpato, Reconstruction and Analysis of the Acoustic Transfer Matrix of a Reheat Flame From Large-Eddy Simulations, Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power 141 (2). doi:10.1115/1.4041151. URL <http://gasturbinespower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?doi=10.1115/1.4041151>
- [3] V. Bellucci, B. Schuermans, D. Nowak, P. Flohr, C. O. Paschereit, Thermoacoustic Modeling of a Gas Turbine Combustor Equipped With Acoustic Dampers, Journal of Turbomachinery 127 (2) (2005) 372–379. doi:10.1115/1.1791284. URL <http://Turbomachinery.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1467006>
- [4] B.-T. Chu, On the generation of pressure waves at a plane flame front, in: International Symposium on Combustion, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, 1952.
- [5] L. S. Chen, S. Bomberg, W. Polifke, On the jump conditions for flow perturbations across a moving heat source, in: 21st International Congress on Sound and Vibration, Beijing, China, 2014. URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260278261_On_the_Jump_Conditions_for_Flow_Perturbations_Across_a_Moving_Heat_Source
- [6] B. Schuermans, V. Bellucci, F. Guethe, F. Meili, P. Flohr, C. O. Paschereit, A Detailed Analysis of Thermoacoustic Interaction Mechanisms in a Turbulent Premixed Flame, in: ASME Paper No. GT2004-53831, Vienna, Austria, 2004. doi:10.1115/GT2004-53831. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?articleid=1636336>
- [7] W. Polifke, A. Poncet, C. Paschereit, K. Döbbling, Reconstruction of acoustic transfer matrices by instationary computational fluid dynamics, Journal of Sound and Vibration 245 (3) (2001) 483–510. doi:10.1006/jsvi.2001.3594. URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022460X01935941>
- [8] A. Scarpato, L. Zander, R. Kulkarni, B. Schuermans, Identification of Multi-Parameter Flame Transfer Function for a Reheat Combustor, in: ASME Paper No. GT2016-57699, Seoul, South Korea, 2016. doi:10.1115/GT2016-57699. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2016-57699>
- [9] M. Zellhuber, B. Schuermans, W. Polifke, Impact of acoustic pressure on autoignition and heat release, Combustion Theory and Modelling 18 (1) (2014) 1–31. doi:10.1080/13647830.2013.817609. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13647830.2013.817609>
- [10] K. Aditya, A. Gruber, C. Xu, T. Lu, A. Krisman, M. R. Bothien, J. H. Chen, Direct numerical simulation of flame stabilization assisted by autoignition in a reheat gas turbine combustor, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute 37 (2) (2018) 2635–2642. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2018.06.084. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1540748918302670>